

Workplace Harassment and Employee Alienation in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between workplace Harassment and employee alienation in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, it measured the relationship between harassment and powerlessness, meaninglessness and self-estrangement. The psychological safety theory was adopted as the theoretical foundations in the study. It adopted the cross-sectional survey design. The study populations were 687 permanent employees from nineteen commercial banks in Rivers State. A sample size of 248 was drawn using Krejcie & Morgan table on sample size determination. 248 copies of questionnaires were personally administered to respondents out of which 218 representing 88% were found valid for the analysis. All items on the questionnaire had a Cronbach Alpha threshold of 0.7 and above in the reliability test. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient computed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used for bivariate analysis respectively. The results showed significant relationship between workplace harassment and measures of employee alienation (powerlessness meaninglessness and self-estrangement). This study concludes that significant relationship exists between workplace harassment and employee alienation which manifests in employee psychological detachment from work, reduced collaboration, stress and depression and lack of connectedness with others. This study recommends that management of commercial banks develop work systems that are duly regulated and controlled for harassment; such that is emphatic of ethics, principles and of zero tolerance of harassment.

Keywords: Workplace Harassment, Psychological safety Theory, Employee Alienation, powerlessness, meaninglessness, self-estrangement

INTRODUCTION

Employees are consequential to the success of organisations. Aside from the creativity, talents, skills and knowledge they bring to the organisations, their performance calls for concern to the managers or business owners whose main aim is to make profit and expand. The manager take into cognizance all that affects the output of the employees that can stall or delay progress (Arubayi & Eruvbedede, 2022). Employee are considered as a nucleus of an organisation, with the responsibility for carrying out daily operations. Thus, they are known as the wholly and solely source of competitive advantage. This is why concerns of employee alienation have continued to trail organisational research, and is considered as a serious bother, because it could affect the organisation's productivity and competitiveness. According to Kurdi (2018) alienation describes a feeling of detachment and the lack of placement within a context. It demonstrates the lack of meaningfulness in roles and relationship with others in the organisation. Kurdi (2018) pointed to experiences of powerlessness, meaninglessness and self-estrangement as the more outstanding and dominant characteristics of employee alienation.

Commercial banks in Nigeria face numerous challenges in line with increasing competitiveness of the industry, with much turbulence from the environment. Such as the pandemic, the great resignation, the need for rapid digital transformation, evolving customer expectations for personalized and seamless services and the escalating threat of cybersecurity. Commercial banks also face challenges in maintaining motivation of workers and retaining their most precious assets (employees) especially with the issue of mass exodus of the working class in Nigeria.. In order to have employees fully involved and engaged at work, banks need to ensure a safe working environment with clear policies and procedures which shows transparency and a value for workers dignity and self-confidence. They need to create such a workplace that is ideal, healthy and free of all those acts and behaviours that makes it hostile and unpleasant for the employees. Among such organisational issues is harassment which is critical and can negatively impact on employee alienation and ultimately affect their collaboration, competitiveness, performance and productivity (Khan, Khan & Khan, 2015).

Matters of workplace harassment recently gained interest among practitioners and researchers as it is becoming one of the most sensitive areas of effective workplace management (Asha & Nithyashree, 2017). Adam cited in Ngwane (2018) delineates harassing behaviour as a persistently negative attack on personal and professional performance, usually unpredictable, irrational and often unfair. Khan et al (2015) defined workplace harassment as dehumanizing, commenting or discouraging an individual...it may also involve unwanted and unwelcomed sexual favours and relationship. Ngwane (2018) asserts that harassment is a particularly serious form of discrimination defined as any action, or practice, by a person or group of people which is unwanted, unwarranted and unappreciated, objectionable and causes humiliation, offence and distress. These issues can harm the employee and organisations as well. He further asserts that workplace harassment is a global phenomenon affecting the morale of employees negatively. A common misconception is that harassment is simply sexual in nature. While it is prominent, harassment includes unfair misuse of power or position generally by a senior member of staff who may display belittling or threatening behaviour towards individual workers or groups of workers. The reality is that harassment is directly responsible for workplace hostility and discord. It must be acknowledged that regardless of position, gender, religion, disability, race or sexual preference, every individual has the right to be free of abusive behaviour. Consequently, if workers are not accorded dignity, harassment can constitute unfair discrimination and therefore, a violation of human rights. Asha and Nithyashree (2017) affirms that harassment is a costly proposition for employers. It can result in low morale, absenteeism, reduced productivity, employee turnover, and damages and litigation costs.

Organisations need to ensure that their practices are not unfavourable and overly demanding, causing employees to feel harassed and bullied. A more ideal and responsive workplace should be created to prevent employees from alienating. According to Khan, Khan and Khan (2015) Harassment policies should be embedded in the culture of the organisation and every employee should be educated on the intolerance of harassment, they, including managers should be aware of acceptable and unacceptable workplace behaviours in order to make a healthy, constructive and conducive workplace. Much research has focused on relating employee alienation with variables like bureaucracy, person-job fit, person-organisation fit, and leadership style, this demonstrates a knowledge gap, expressed in the scarcity of studies, which have studied

workplace harassment and its effect on employee alienation, especially within the context of commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria. This study, as a departure from previous studies, thus addressed the relationship between workplace harassment and employee alienation.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Workplace Harassment and Employee Alienation of commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Source: Researcher’s Conceptualization from Review of Related Literature, 2025.

Objective of the study

The objective of this study was to examine the relationship between workplace harassment and employee alienation in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Determine the relationship between workplace harassment and powerlessness in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria
- ii. Examine the relationship between workplace harassment and meaningfulness in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria
- iii. Ascertain the relationship between workplace harassment and self-estrangement in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions were put in line with addressing the relationship between workplace harassment behaviour and employee alienation. These are stated as follows:

- (i) What is the relationship between harassment behaviour and employee powerlessness in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- (ii) What is the relationship between harassment behaviour and employee meaninglessness in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- (iii) What is the relationship between harassment behaviour and employee self-estrangement in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are stated:

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between harassment and powerlessness in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between harassment and meaninglessness in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria.

HO₃: There is no significant relationship between harassment and self-estrangement in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Harassment

Harassment describes a behaviour that is persistent, abusive, uncivil and physical assault directed against a single employee or a group of employees (Williams, 2001). Shetty and Nithyashree (2017) defined workplace harassment as a belittling or threatening behaviour directed at an individual worker or a group of workers. Harassment is any improper and unwelcome conduct that might reasonably be expected to cause offence and humiliation to another person Unnikrishnan, Rekha, Kumar, Reshmi, Mithra & Sanjeev (2010). Ngwane (2018) argued that individual targeted for workplace harassment is based on their diversity in gender, race, ethnic origin, nationality, religion, political affiliation or sexuality and can be considered as a serious

crime. Lockwood and Marda (2014) asserts that harassment manifest in behaviour such as: false accusations, excessive criticism and over monitoring of work. Itulua-Abumere (2021) asserts that harassment manifest in sexual harassment, offensive jokes, offensive pictures, assault, ridicule, intimidation, excessive monitoring, practical jokes, unfairly altering job responsibility, strict criticism and obstructing promotions. It creates poor relations, lower morale, poor attentiveness in workplaces. All forms of toxic behaviours, particularly harassment and bullying reports significantly high levels of depression, anxiety and exhaustion (Pauksztat, Salin & Kitada, 2022). Tehrani (2004) asserts that workplace harassment behaviours has recently attracted the interest of researchers, scholars and practitioners, since it has become one of the most essential aspect of successful workplace management, as harassment is a substantial source of work stress.

Employee Alienation

Karl Marx, among numerous theorist was the proponent of the theory of alienation, meaning the feeling of an outsider or feeling a sense of isolation, strangeness or feeling of having no external connection. To Hegel and Feuerbach, Alienation means an intellectual phenomenon that emanates from an inaccurate view of the world. But to Karl Marx it is a social and material process. He used his alienation theory to describe the division of being or objects that are immanently together. From his study of economic and philosophic book of 1844 Marx explored alienation from a political, anthropological and socio-cultural view. Via Karl Marx's philosophical perspective than economic; he explained how he is isolated from the capitalist mode of production from work and other workers. This definition has become widely acceptable and useful in psychology, sociology and political science. Marx (1978) defined alienation as a sense of powerlessness, meaninglessness, self-estrangement and isolation experienced by human beings and a feeling of being oppressed.

Researchers have given meaning to alienation in description of contemporary and modern day phenomenon such as the definition of Dipietro and Pizam (2008) which asserts that alienation is a cognitive sense of separation from work and the workplace, which reflected in a lack of job involvement and organisational identification. Matheson (2007) defined alienation as a state of psychological detachment from work. To alienate is to experience a lack of connection or disconnection, detachment, aloofness, separation, removal or distancing of self from a situation or target (Dipietro & Pizam, 2008). According to Kanungo (1979) alienation is the separation of a person from other component of his environment. Alienation occurs when employee perceive

that the work environment is personally detrimental to their needs, values and sense of organisational well-being. Employee alienation describes a state of being in which employees are demotivated and apathetic toward their work. They feel alienated or separated from co-workers, supervisors, managers and employers and lacks passion for the work that they are required to do (Kanungo, 1979)

Measures of Employee Alienation

Powerlessness

Powerlessness is the first measure of employee alienation adopted in the study, it describes the extent to which the employee experiences a lack of control over their situation or condition (Kurdi, 2018). According to Kakabadse (1986), Seeman (1959) and Aiken and Hage (1966) cited in Sarros, Tanewski, Winter and Joseph (2003) powerlessness represents ‘the expectancy or probability held by the individual that his own behaviour cannot determine the occurrence of the reinforcement he seeks’. Simply, powerlessness can be measured with a lack of job autonomy and participation, workers lack freedom to exercise control over issues that concerns them and their work activities. Employees’ inability to address the system or their circumstances, deprives them of their rights to address issues that hurt them. This way they feel worthless and lose their self-esteem or confidence (Kurdi, 2018).

Meaninglessness

This measure refers to the employees feeling of disenchantment with their work and with the organisation. Seeman cited in Tummer, Bekkers, Thiel & Steijn (2014) argues that meaninglessness occurs when a person cannot comprehend the events in which he or she is involved. In a work environment, meaninglessness arises when workers are not able to understand the ambiguous system of goals in the organisation and its relationship to their own work. When employees feel disenchanting with their work, their lack of meaning points to their emotional disengagement with their work, hence a lack of satisfaction and commitment to their roles (Vinokurov & Kozhina, 2020). Meaninglessness suggests that the employees view their position, placement in the organisation, work and roles in the organisation as lacking in essence and void of inspiration; hence such offer no real substantial value or purpose to the employee (Vinokurov & Kozhina, 2020).

Self-Estrangement

Third measure of alienation describes the worker or employee's loss of self and their lack of placement in the organisation. It describes a condition in which workers no longer consider themselves as part of the organisation and that way, tend to act or behave in ways that often do not conform to the norms and beliefs of the organisation (Kurdi, 2018). O'Donohue and Nelson (2014) asserts that self-estrangement is a detachment or sense of identity or personal fulfillment. The effects of loneliness and isolation may culminate in estrangement in respect to both personal and social identities. Bluner in O'Donohue et al (2014) views self-estrangement in terms of feelings of detachment or sense of no identity and impersonal/personal fulfillment. The effects of estrangement deprives us from being with other people.

Theoretical Foundations of the Study

Psychological Safety Theory (PST) is the theory adopted in this study. The theory was developed by Professor Amy Edmondson in the early 1999, who explores the importance of creating a work environment where employees feel safe to take interpersonal risks without fear of negative consequences. The formal definition of psychological safety was chronicled by Maslow in his hierarchy of needs as "a kind of feeling of confidence, safety, freedom and a detachment from fear and anxiety." (Maslow, 1945 cited in Chen, Gao, Zheng & Ran 2015). Minxi (2002) cited in Chen et al (2015) viewed the psychological climate as individual level variables, "the process reaction of individual characteristics, involved in cognition, concept formation and the work environment". Employees might explain events, speculate the possible results, and take the next logical behavior in accordance with their perceived psychological climate (James & James, 1979 in Chen et al 2015).

According to Mortorn, Cogan, Kolaez, and Nikolic, (2021). Psychological safety is increasingly recognised as central to mental health & wellbeing. PST is analysed and defined in three categories: individual, group and organisation. When employees see the workplace as helpful to their well-being, psychological safety is perceived. Further, psychological safety refers to the employees' awareness of the high freedom of safety and not to worry about damaging self-image, organisational status or career development (Jones & James, 1979 cited in Chen et al, 2015). leadership behaviour is the most effective predictor variables for employee psychological safety. Kahn (1990) also opined that management style is correlated with individual

psychological safety, supportive and open style may play a promoting role on the latter. The Psychological Safety Theory applies to the problem of this research as it explains the expectation of safety between: coworkers, superordinate and subordinate and organisation and employees. In a workplace where harassment exist, employees may experience a lack of psychological safety, where they feel unable to voice their concerns, offer suggestions or challenge the harasser. This lack of psychological safety can lead to employee alienation, as individuals may feel stifled, unheard, and disconnected from their work and organisation. The implication of Psychological Safety Theory (PST) to this study is that: harassment can severely undermine psychological safety in the workplace.

Empirical Review

Workplace Harassment Behaviour and Employee Alienation

Ngwane (2018) investigated the impact of harassment on employees performance at a South African Higher Education Institute with a total population of 1319 full-time staff at the selected HEI (both academic and academic support) and a sample of 200 was selected. These included members of management, academic and non-academic staff in all six faculties. An equal balance of males and females. African, Coloured, Indian and White staff were selected in proportion to their respective numerical distribution in the institution. The study shows evidence for workplace harassment having a detrimental impact at individual, organisational and societal levels. The results of the study should assist management in recognising the need to urgently establish and implement procedures to deal with the negative impact of harassment in the workplace.

Rokonuzzaman, Ali and Moral (2019) studied the effects of workplace harassment on the relationship amongst co-workers and their work engagement in a developing country with a sample size of 208 from Bangladesh of which 47% were female and 53% were male. IBM AMOS based Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used to obtain the results. Evidence from the study shows that there is severe experience of harassment in workplaces in Bangladesh which negatively influences their relationship with co-workers and resulted in poor engagement.

Arubayi (2023) opined that harassment is the atrocious act of undermining a person or groups of workers by merciless, spiteful, cruel, or embarrassment tactics. It is illegal and also a form of

discrimination to harass someone verbally or physically based on their gender, age, religion, or ethnicity. Someone is harassing you if he (or she) does things to make you feel uncomfortable, says things to make you feel awkward, or puts you in danger in some way. The harasser, on the other hand, may choose the gender, race, age, appearance, sexual performance, handicap, faiths, beliefs, family, birthplace, or political convictions to make the victim feel uneasy (Ontario Women's Directorate, 2018 cited in Arubayi, 2023).

METHODOLOGY

The researcher utilised the cross-sectional survey as the research design for this investigation. The accessible population for this research was made up of six hundred and eighty-seven (687) permanent employees who are involved in routine duties from 19 commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study in this vein focused on the main branches of the 19 commercial banks with national and international licence in Rivers State, Nigeria. The Krejcie and Morgan sample size determination table was adopted. The sample size was determined by matching the given population of 687 employees to the corresponding number of 248 on the Krejcie and Morgan's table.) A 20-item questionnaire was used as the primary instrument of data collection. All variables were structured in a five-point Likert Scale: 5 = Strongly Agreed, 4 = Agreed, 3 = Undecided, 2 = Disagreed and 1 = Strongly Disagreed to measure workplace toxic behaviour and employee alienation. Test of normality and necessary reliability and validity tests were performed to explain the trustworthiness of the measurement instruments. Data generated from the copies of the questionnaire were analysed using frequency tables, percentage, mean and standard deviation. In testing the hypotheses, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used.

Table 3.2: Cronbach Alpha Reliability Test Results of Valid Questionnaire

Variables	Measures	No. of Items	Alpha Values
Workplace Harassment		5	0.838
Employee alienation	Powerlessness	5	0.895
	Meaninglessness	5	0.859
	Self-Estrangement	5	0.850

Source: Research Data, 2025.

Bivariate Analysis (testing of Hypotheses)

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between workplace harassment and powerlessness.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between workplace harassment and meaninglessness.

HO₃: There is no significant relationship between workplace harassment and self-estrangement.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 2: Workplace Harassment and employee alienation

		Workplace Harassment	Powerlessness	Meaninglessness	Self-Estrangement
Workplace Harassment	Pearson Correlation	1	.908**	.834**	.780**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	218	218	218	218
Powerlessness	Pearson Correlation	.908**	1	.839**	.873**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	218	218	218	218
Meaninglessness	Pearson Correlation	.834**	.839**	1	.886**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	218	218	218	218
Self-Estrangement	Pearson Correlation	.780**	.873**	.886**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	218	218	218	218

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data, 2025

Table 2 shows the result on the assessment of the relationship between harassment behaviour and the measures of employee alienation. The outcome of the analysis show that harassment behaviour significantly contributes toward the outcomes of powerlessness (R = 0.908 and P = 0.000), meaninglessness (R = 0.834 and P = 0.000) and self-estrangement (R = 0.780 and P = 0.000). The outcome from the analysis thus demonstrates the significance of harassment behaviour and its impact on outcomes of employee alienation. Thus the null hypothetical statements earlier postulated are rejected and the alternate accepted as follows:

H₁: There is a significant relationship between workplace harassment and employee powerlessness in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria.

H₂: There is a significant relationship between workplace harassment and employee meaningfulness in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria.

H₃: There is a significant relationship between workplace harassment and employee self-estrangement in commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Workplace Harassment and Employee Alienation H₀₁-H₀₃

The result reveals that workplace harassment and employee alienation of permanent employees in commercial banks in Rivers State are significantly related. The significant relationship affirms harassment behaviour as a correlate of employee alienation implying that abuse, personal criticism, excessive supervision and demand on employees at work influence employees' expression of alienation thereby creating feelings of powerlessness, meaningfulness and self estrangement of workers. This suggest that existence of harassment in the workplace mitigates the conduciveness of the work environment. It denies the employees the opportunity to socialise, be supportive, be devoted, collaborate, get enthusiastic and exert their full potentials willingly.

Findings as established by empirical data supports positions of earlier studies concerning the nexus between harassment behaviour and employee alienation. Johny (2023) reported harassment in the workplace as a toxic behaviour that causes stress, emotional burnout, anxiety, and depression because of the negative emotions that arise as a result of harassment. This corroborates with Arubayi (2023) claim that workplace harassment is a widespread occurrence which has a significant impact on the mental health of employees and workers. Workplace harassment behaviour can be sourced from any level of employee in the organization, meaning it could emanate from managers, supervisors, co-workers or even customers and clients who interface with workers. Paoli and Merllie (2001) revealed that harassment in the workplace has a negative impact on employee morale and may be quite disruptive to their performance. Arubayi (2023) opined that harassment in the workplace occurs often in the form of mobbing and bullying, which gravely undermines a person's dignity, integrity, and ability. Further, harassment behaviour has a negative impact on organizational performance. The implication of the high

impact of workplace harassment on employee alienation in commercial banks affects employee – supervisor (line managers) relationship and/or employee –employee relations. The existence of harassment in commercial banks as evident in this research. Increases the level of victimization and the violation of the rights of workers to be free of abusive behaviour. The findings of the study should assist management in recognizing the urgent need in establishing and implementing procedures to deal with the negative impact of harassment in the organization and to develop a workplace environment that is committed to fostering transparency, equality and respect for human dignity. This findings if ignored, would lead to consequences that are detrimental to both the employee and the organization. The finding also clearly indicated the significant association between harassment and employee alienation from work and others.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The findings of this study validates generally held opinions that the level of toxicity in the workplace negatively influences employee experience, relationships and perceptions of others in their organisation leading to their feeling of alienation. Harassment behaviour in the workplace influences employee alienation of powerlessness, meaninglessness and self-estrangement. This behaviour is found to be a widespread occurrence that has significant impact on the mental health of employees as this behaviour by leaders and coworkers persistently assault personal dedication to work and is a significant source of stress. Harassment increases bad working relationship, reduced moral, dignity and spirit. Based on the results and conclusions of this study as it relates to the permanent staff of commercial banks in Rivers State, this study recommends as follows: Managers and policy makers should develop and reinforce zero harassment policies, and ensure its implementation in the workplace and also investigate all harassment complaints.

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